

HOMBALE IN PREGNANCY: AN AYURVEDIC PERSPECTIVE ON MATERNAL–FETAL NUTRITION

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ABSTRACT

Background: Optimal maternal nutrition plays a key role in fetal growth, placental development, and prevention of obstetric complications. Ayurveda emphasizes *Masanumasika Garbhini Paricharya* (month-specific dietary protocols) for *Garbha Vriddhi* and maternal wellbeing. *Hombale*, the inflorescence of the coconut tree, is traditionally recommended during pregnancy as a nutrient-dense formulation. **Objective:** To review the nutritional composition, Ayurvedic rationale, clinical relevance, preparation method, and therapeutic potential of *Hombale* administration in pregnancy. **Methods:** Classical Ayurvedic texts describing *Garbhini Paricharya* were reviewed alongside contemporary nutritional and biomedical literature on maternal–fetal nutrition. The ingredients of *Hombale* were analyzed for macronutrients, micronutrients, bioactive compounds, and their relevance to fetal development, and correlated with Ayurvedic principles of *Garbhaposhana*.

Results: *Hombale* contains essential micronutrients and

antioxidants that may support fetal growth, improve uteroplacental circulation, enhance maternal strength, and regulate metabolic responses. When administered during 3rd, 5th, and 7th months of pregnancy, it aligns with critical stages of fetal organ development.

Conclusion: *Hombale* is a promising traditional nutritional supplement with physiological

benefits in pregnancy. Controlled clinical studies are needed to validate its effectiveness in preventing complications such as IUGR and oligohydramnios.

KEYWORDS: *Hombale*, coconut inflorescence, pregnancy nutrition, fetal growth, prenatal diet.

INTRODUCTION

Pregnancy is a physiological state characterized by increased metabolic, nutritional, and endocrine requirements. Inadequate maternal nutrition is associated with complications such as intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR), low birth weight, anemia, pre-eclampsia, and developmental disorders. Global estimates indicate that nearly 14.7% of all births are born with low birth weight each year.^[1] Low birth weight is associated with markedly higher risks of neonatal morbidity and mortality, impaired growth, and long-term metabolic and cognitive disorders.^[2] Inadequate maternal dietary diversity has been shown to increase the odds of Low birth weight by 1.7 times.^[3] Conversely, improved maternal diet quality and appropriate gestational weight gain significantly reduce the incidence of Low Birth Weight.^[4] These observations emphasize the crucial role of adequate prenatal nutrition in ensuring healthy pregnancy outcomes. Ayurveda emphasizes a structured dietary regimen for pregnant women to support *Garbha Vriddhi* and maternal strength. *Masanumasika Garbhini Paricharya* (month-specific dietary protocols) ensures optimal nourishment of the developing fetus.

Across various regions of India, numerous traditional nutritional practices have been followed for generations, focusing on enhancing maternal health and fetal development through culturally rooted dietary formulations and time-tested nutraceutical preparations. Among these traditional nutritional interventions, *Hombale* holds a significant role, particularly in the coastal regions of Karnataka, where it is administered during pregnancy as a specialized nourishment-enhancing formulation.

***Masanumasika Garbhini Paricharya* and the Concept of *Garbha Vriddhi*^[5]**

Masanumasika Garbhini Paricharya refers to the systematic, month-wise approach to antenatal care described in classical Ayurvedic texts, wherein dietary substances are selected according to the developmental needs of the fetus and the physiological status of the mother. Each month is associated with specific milestones, such as organ differentiation, tissue accretion, and development of strength and vitality (*Bala* and *Ojas*).

Ayurveda predominantly advocates *Madhura Rasa, Snigdha, Guru, and Brimhana* substances during pregnancy, as these qualities support anabolic processes, nourish *Dhatus*, and pacify *Vata*, which is physiologically dominant during gestation. These principles provide the theoretical basis for the use of nutrient-dense, easily digestible formulations such as Hombale.

Hombale: Concept, Composition

Hombale is a traditional antenatal nutritional preparation prepared using tender coconut inflorescence (*Cocos nucifera*) as the principal component, supplemented with dry fruits (almond, cashew, walnut, black raisins), milk, rock sugar, saffron, and *Pravala Pishti*. It is customarily prepared fresh and administered in moderate quantities during specific months of pregnancy.

Table No 1- List of ingredients for Hombale with Karma.^[6,7]

SL NO	INGREDIENT	KARMA
1	Hombale	<i>Brimhana, Balya, Garbhaposhaka, Trishnahara</i>
2	Almonds	<i>Brimhana, Medhya, Balya</i>
3	Cashew	<i>Brimhana, Balya</i>
4	Black Raisins	<i>Raktavardhaka, Brimhana.</i>
5	Walnut	<i>Medhya, Brimhana, Balya.</i>
6	Kesari	<i>Medhya, Hridya, Varnya</i>
7	Rock Sugar	<i>Brimhana, Trishnashamaka, Dahahara</i> According to <i>Bhava Prakasha</i> it is a “ <i>Swabhvataha hitakara Dravya</i> ”.
8	<i>Pravala Pishti</i>	<i>Asthiposhaka, Raktapittashamaka, Balya</i>
9	Milk	<i>Jeevaniya, Brimhana, Ojavardhaka</i>

Fig. 1: Hombale *Cocos nucifera* (Inflorescence)

Fig. 2: Almonds *Prunus dulcis* (Mill.) D.A. Webb

Fig. 3: Cashew *Anacardium occidentale* L.

Fig. 4: Black Raisin
Vitis vinifera L. (dried fruit)

Fig 5- Walnut *Juglans regia* L.

Fig. 6: Kesari *Crocus sativus* L

Fig 7- Rock Sugar

Fig. 8: *Pravala Pishti*
Coral calcium

Fig 9- Milk

Table No. 2: Phytochemical/nutrients and its Pregnancy relevant mode of action.

Ingredient	Major phytochemicals / nutrients	Pregnancy relevant mode of action
Coconut inflorescence (<i>Cocos nucifera</i> L.)	Proanthocyanidins (condensed tannins), flavonoids, phenolics, carbohydrates.	Ethyl-acetate-soluble proanthocyanidins show progestogenic activity, increasing progesterone and modulating estrogen in female rats, which can help stabilize endometrium and reduce menorrhagia; polyphenolic antioxidants may lower reproductive-tract oxidative stress and support a favourable uterine environment for implantation and pregnancy maintenance. ^[8,9]
Almond (<i>Prunus dulcis</i>)	Lipids rich in MUFA, some PUFA; protein; vitamin E; folate; magnesium; polyphenols.	Prenatal almond feeding in rats increased hippocampal and prefrontal BDNF and phospho-CREB and inhibited MAO-A/B, leading to better memory, reduced anxiety-like behaviour and improved stress adaptation in offspring, indicating neurotrophic and neuroprotective actions beneficial for fetal brain development; nuts in human cohorts provide folate and essential fatty acids that accumulate in fetal neural tissue and correlate with better child neuropsychological scores. ^[10]
Cashew nut (<i>Anacardium occidentale</i>)	Carbohydrates; proteins; MUFA (oleic acid) and PUFA (linoleic acid); magnesium, zinc, copper; phenolic compounds.	Provides essential fatty acids used for neuronal membrane and retinal phospholipid synthesis; magnesium, zinc and copper support antioxidant enzymes and erythropoiesis, thereby contributing to maternal energy metabolism and oxygen carrying capacity, indirectly supporting placental

		and fetal growth. ^[11]
Black raisins (<i>Vitis vinifera</i> dried)	Iron; B-complex vitamins; potassium; carbohydrates; flavonoids and phenolic.	In anemic rats, black raisin extract significantly increased Hb, RBC count and improved blood film morphology versus anemic controls, showing a hematonic effect useful for iron-deficiency anemia in pregnancy; flavonoid antioxidants also improve splenic immune markers, potentially supporting maternal immune. ^[12]
Walnut (<i>Juglans regia</i>)	High α -linolenic acid (ω -3 ALA); PUFA; protein; folate; vitamin E; polyphenols	ω -3 ALA is a precursor of DHA/EPA, essential for neurogenesis, synaptogenesis and retinal development; human and animal data show that adequate maternal ω -3 improves offspring visual and cognitive outcomes, while deficiency impairs neurodevelopment, so walnut intake can support fetal CNS and eye development; antioxidants may modulate maternal inflammation and oxidative stress. ^[13]
Saffron (<i>Crocus sativus</i>)	Crocin, crocetin (water-soluble carotenoids); safranal; picrocrocin	Crocin and saffron extracts show strong antioxidant and anti-inflammatory actions and are neuroprotective in brain injury and dementia models, improving memory and reducing neuronal apoptosis; at low, culinary doses this suggests potential support for maternal CNS and indirectly fetal neurodevelopment, although high-dose saffron/crocin in pregnant rats has been reported to lower progesterone and alter gonadotropins, so pharmacological doses are not recommended in pregnancy. ^[14,15]
Rock sugar (Sharkara)	Sucrose (glucose + fructose)	Provides rapidly absorbable carbohydrate for maternal energy and placental glucose transfer; when taken with fiber- and fat-containing foods, post-prandial glycaemic rise is moderated, helping maintain euglycaemia important for normal fetal growth. ^[16]
Pravala Pishti (coral calcium)	Calcium carbonate with trace elements (Mg, Sr, etc.)	Coral calcium acts as a bioavailable calcium source; adequate maternal calcium intake reduces risk of hypertensive disorders of pregnancy and supports fetal skeletal mineralisation and maternal bone preservation. ^[17]
Cow's milk	Casein and whey proteins; lactose; saturated and MUFA fats; calcium; phosphorus; vitamins D, B12, A	Higher maternal milk/dairy intake is associated with increased birth weight and length, likely via high-quality protein and IGF-1 pathways; calcium and vitamin D support fetal bone formation and maternal skeletal health, and lactose enhances calcium absorption. ^[18]

Table 3: NUTRITIONAL PROFILE OF HOMBALE.

Sl no	Ingredient	Major Macronutrients	Key Vitamins	Key Trace Elements	Fatty Acid Profile	Bioactive Compounds	Glycaemic Relevance
1	Coconut inflorescence (tender)	Carbohydrates, protein	Vit C, B-complex	K, Mg	Minimal fat	Polyphenols	Provides quick energy without heavy glycaemic load
2	Almond	Protein, fat, fibres	Vit E, B2, folate	Mg, Ca, Zn	MUFA-rich	Flavonoids	Low-moderate Glycemic Index,

							stabilizes glucose
3	Cashew	Carbs, protein, fat	B6, folate	Cu, Mg, Zn, Fe	MUFA, PUFA	Polyphenols	Moderate Glycemic Index; balanced energy
4	Black raisins	Carbohydrates, fibres	B-complex	Fe, K, Ca	Negligible fat	Polyphenols	Natural sugars, gradual glucose release
5	Walnut	Fat, protein, fibres	B6, folate	Mg, P, Mn	Omega-3 (ALA)	Polyphenols	Low Glycemic Index
6	Rock sugar (<i>Sharkara</i>)	Carbohydrates	—	—	—	—	Rapid glucose source
7	Saffron (<i>Kesari</i>)	Minor carbs, protein	Vit A precursors	Mn, K	Minimal fat	Crocin, crocetin, safranal	Negligible Glycemic Index (used in microdose)
8	Pravala Piṣṭi	—	—	Ca (bioavailable)	—	Trace minerals	No glycaemic effect
9	Milk (cow's milk)	Protein, fat, lactose	B12, A, D	Ca, P	Saturated + MUFA	—	Low Glycemic Index

Method of Preparation

Hombale is prepared by finely grinding all ingredients, namely tender coconut inflorescence, almonds, cashew nuts, black raisins, walnuts, saffron, rock sugar, and *Pravala Piṣṭi* into a uniform paste, which is then added to warm milk to obtain a homogenous, palatable drink intended for antenatal consumption.

It is typically prepared fresh and administered once daily.

Figure 10 Mixture of all ingredients.

Figure 11 Hombale Drink.

Time of administration

- For 3 consecutive days in 3rd, 5th and 7th month of gestation.
- Empty stomach.

BENEFITS

- Enhancement of Maternal Nutritional Status.
- Supports fetal Growth and Weight Gain.
- Promotion of fetal Neurodevelopment.
- Prevention of Maternal fatigue and Debility.
- Improvement of maternal hematological status.
- Support of skeletal development in the fetus.
- Prepares body for lactation.

DISCUSSION

Clinical Relevance in Modern Obstetrics

In contemporary obstetric practice, nutritional inadequacy remains a key contributor to low birth weight, borderline IUGR, anemia, and poor gestational weight gain. Hombale may serve as an adjunct nutritional intervention in antenatal care, particularly in women with inadequate dietary intake or increased nutritional demands.

It should be emphasized that Hombale is not intended to replace standard antenatal nutritional supplements or medical management but may complement existing strategies to improve pregnancy outcomes.

Harmonizing Hombale with *Masanumasika Garbha Vriddhi* and *Garbhini Paricharya*

Ayurveda conceptualizes pregnancy nutrition through a holistic lens, wherein *Ahara* is regarded as *Oushadha*, capable of influencing not only physical growth but also metabolic, immunological, and epigenetic pathways. *Masanumasika Garbhini Paricharya* provides a structured framework that synchronizes maternal diet with fetal developmental milestones, ensuring *Uttara-uttara Dhatu Poshana* and optimal *Garbha Vriddhi*.^[19]

The principles elucidated in *Garbhini Paricharya* highlight that fetal nourishment occurs through *Ahara Rasa*, which is selectively distributed via *Kedara-Kulya Nyaya*. This selective transfer ensures that nutrients are utilized according to the specific requirements of the developing fetus, placenta, and maternal tissues. Hombale, being *Madhura rasa* predominant and *Snigdha* in nature, supports *Rasa Dhatu Poshana*, thereby indirectly nourishing *Rakta*, *Mamsa*, and *Medo Dhatus*, which are critical during the mid-trimester phases of pregnancy.

The administration of Hombale during the 3rd, 5th, and 7th months closely mirrors the rationale of *Masanumasika Garbha Vriddhi*.

- ❖ The third month is characterized by differentiation of *Sarva Anga-Pratyanga* and sensory organ development, wherein easily assimilable carbohydrates, micronutrients, and antioxidants support cellular differentiation and neurodevelopment.
- ❖ The fifth month marks *Mamsa-Shonita Upachaya* and heightened anabolic activity, necessitating increased intake of proteins and healthy fats, which are adequately provided by the dry fruits and milk base of Hombale.
- ❖ The seventh month represents a phase of *Klanta Shareera* for the mother and functional maturation of fetal organs, especially the nervous and respiratory systems, during which *Brimhana* and *Balya Ahara* aids accumulation of *Bala* and *Ojas*.

Table 4: Rationale for Hombale Administration.

Gestational Month	Ayurvedic Concept (Masanumasika Garbha Vriddhi)	Key Fetal / Maternal Changes	Rationale for Hombale Administration
3rd Month	<i>Sarva Anga-Pratyanga Vibhaga</i>	Differentiation of organs and sense organs; initiation of neurodevelopment	Easily assimilable carbohydrates, micronutrients, and antioxidants in Hombale support cellular differentiation, early neurodevelopment, and stabilization of pregnancy
5th Month	<i>Mamsa-Shonita Upachaya</i>	Rapid fetal growth with increased anabolic activity; development of muscle and blood tissues	Proteins, healthy fats, and minerals from dry fruits and milk in Hombale aid <i>Mamsa Dhatu Vriddhi</i> , enhance uteroplacental nourishment, and prevent maternal depletion
7th Month	<i>Klaanta Shareera and Ojas Vriddhi</i>	Maternal fatigue; functional maturation of fetal organs, especially nervous and respiratory systems	<i>Brimhana</i> and <i>Balya</i> properties of Hombale promote accumulation of <i>Bala</i> and <i>Ojas</i> , supporting maternal strength and fetal readiness for extrauterine life

Evidence from Contemporary Research Supporting the Ingredients of Hombale

Contemporary animal and human studies on individual ingredients (nuts, black raisins, milk, saffron, coconut inflorescence) demonstrate hematinic, neurotrophic, antioxidant and progestogenic effects relevant to maternal–fetal outcomes, supporting the theoretical rationale for Hombale as an adjunct pregnancy nutraceutical.

Contraindications and Precautions

Although Hombale is a traditional nutritional preparation and is generally well tolerated, certain precautions and contraindications should be considered in clinical practice.

Hombale should be used with caution or avoided in pregnant women with a known allergy or hypersensitivity to nuts, as it contains almonds, cashew, walnuts, and raisins, which may precipitate allergic reactions. In women with gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) or impaired glucose tolerance, the preparation should be modified or restricted due to the presence of carbohydrate-rich ingredients such as coconut inflorescence and rock sugar, which may contribute to postprandial hyperglycemia.

Caution is advised in cases of excessive gestational weight gain or obesity, as Hombale is an energy-dense formulation and may further increase caloric intake if consumed indiscriminately. In women with severe nausea, vomiting, or hyperemesis gravidarum, tolerance to the preparation may be reduced, and its use should be deferred until symptoms improve.

From an Ayurvedic perspective, Hombale may not be suitable in conditions of *Kapha-Pradhana Prakriti*, *Ama* dominant states, or *Mandagni*, where *Guru* and *Snigdha* substances can aggravate digestive disturbances. In such cases, dosage reduction or temporary avoidance is advisable.

Hombale should not be considered a substitute for standard antenatal nutritional supplements or medical management, particularly in high-risk pregnancies, and its use should be individualized based on maternal nutritional status and clinical condition.

Limitations and Future Research

The existing evidence supporting Hombale is primarily based on traditional knowledge and nutritional rationale. There is a lack of standardized preparation methods, dosage guidelines, and controlled clinical trials. Future research should focus on evaluating its safety, efficacy, and role in preventing adverse pregnancy outcomes through well-designed clinical studies.

CONCLUSION

Hombale is a traditional, nutrient-dense dietary formulation aligned with Ayurvedic principles of *Garbhini Paricharya*. Its composition and pharmacodynamic properties suggest potential benefits in supporting maternal nutrition and fetal growth during pregnancy. Integration of

such traditional nutritional practices with modern antenatal care, supported by scientific validation, may contribute to improved maternal and neonatal outcomes.

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